

ESSENTIAL ISSUES OF HISTORY TEACHING IN THE AGE OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract. In the article, the ongoing reforms in the study of history for young people, the issues of improving the historical literacy of young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan were scientifically discussed, and conclusions and recommendations were developed.

Key words: History, Uzbekistan, historical literacy, independence

ВАЖНЕЙШИЕ ВОПРОСЫ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИСТОРИИ В ЭПОХУ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ

Аннотация. В статье научно обсуждены проводимые реформы в изучении истории для молодежи, вопросы повышения исторической грамотности молодежи в Республике Узбекистан, разработаны выводы и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: История, Узбекистан, историческая грамотность, независимость

INTRODUCTION

Today, global problems, which surprise and worry the people of the world with their various, colorful changes, throw humanity into a whirlwind of many trials. In some regions of the world, natural disasters are escalating, and humanity is suffering from these disasters, and in some regions, human trafficking, extremism and terrorism, arms trade, drug addiction, social inequality, and gender problems are on the rise. Therefore, in the fight against such violence, which brings to mind the international community and international organizations, it shows that not certain organizations or hegemonic countries, but the whole humanity should fight to ensure its dignity, rights and freedom.

This creates many difficulties in the implementation of our reforms aimed at building a people-friendly state and a just civil society.

During the years of independence, as a result of the effective research of Uzbek scientists, previously unknown pages of our national history were opened, many aspects of our historical past were discovered. As a result, history restored its ancient task of serving the people as a science and the spiritual development of the society. The role of historical components in the formation of national ideology and spiritual and moral integrity is incomparable. The educational and educational task of the science of history also serves to form these components in young people. In accordance with the Law "On Education" and the "National Program of Personnel Training", the "Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" for the years 2021-2025, it is necessary to ensure the continuity and consistency of the educational stages, to create a modern methodology of education, and to train future history teachers based on them. requires increasing competence. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 started a new stage of development. According to him, great

importance is attached to the further improvement of the continuous education system, increasing the possibilities of quality education services, as well as raising the qualification level of pedagogues and specialists in this regard.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. In Mirziyoyev's work entitled "We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level" it is written that "We will continue the state policy on youth without deviating, and we will raise this policy to the high level required by today's times as our highest priority. We will mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our country and society so that our young people can become independent thinkers, have high intellectual and spiritual potential, become people who are not inferior to their peers in any field of the world, and be happy." it is a sign that attention is being paid. Therefore, the progress and development of our country, its place in the world community, and the guarantees of its future depend on the level of historical knowledge, national consciousness and historical culture of our youth today. Also, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's greetings to the teachers and trainers of Uzbekistan in his work "We will continue our path of national development with determination and raise it to a new level", "... at the same time, we all understand that more important and urgent tasks are ahead of us today. In this regard, to further strengthen the material and technical base of the field of science and education, to ensure that it is not only in sync with the times, but also ahead of the times, to make extensive use of advanced methods of training and retraining of pedagogic personnel, to carry out these works in cooperation with prestigious centers abroad, "Our state will mobilize all the possibilities to introduce modern technologies in the field, to implement the tasks related to encouraging the hard and responsible work of teachers and teachers, in short, to perfect our new generation, which is entering our lives with great strength."

Teaching history is an important means of inculcating the national idea in young people and forming a scientific worldview in them, preparing them for a correct understanding of the essence of the main trends and conflicts of modern development. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education dated September 23, 2020 was adopted in order to further improve this issue and create a system that ensures that not only the growing youth, but also all citizens of our country have historical value. The purpose of adopting this law is, first of all, to improve the system of historical education and training among young people, to make students respect the history of our country, and to increase the national values and culture of our youth. The process of teaching history is enhanced in two ways.

The first is the observation method. When using this method, various educational-methodical literatures, students' written works, reports, their answers, evaluations and conclusions of teaching are introduced, lessons are observed, and students' knowledge and skills are studied. Thus, when using the observation method, the researcher does not deviate from the current experience of history teaching, he naturally observes and studies it.

Thus, the teaching of history has endless possibilities for developing the national consciousness of students, educating them in the spirit of noble traditions such as national pride and pride, patriotism, humanity, and high spirituality. Therefore, improving the quality and efficiency of educational institutions based on the introduction of international standards for assessing the quality of education and teaching is one of the main issues at the level of state policy

today. Paying great attention to independent thinking in the improvement of the state policy on youth is a priority task of the state.

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